

PERCEPTIONS OF PERSONS BELONGING TO (SOCIAL) MINORITIES ON THE LEGITIMACY OF CRISIS MANAGEMENT DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC: PRESENTATION OF FIELD RESEARCH RESULTS

DELIVERABLE 4.3

WP4: Legitimate Crisis Governance in the Context of Human, Rights, Minority Rights and the Principle of Non-Discrimination

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Executive Summary

This Deliverable includes the Introductory Explanatory Note and the texts of two scholarly articles already submitted for publication to independent peer-reviewed scholarly journals:

Deliverable 4.3.1

Žagar, M. (2024). Perceptions of Persons belonging to (Social) Minorities on the Legitimacy of Crisis Management during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Presentation of Field Research Results. (Submitted for publication in June 2024 to the journal *Teorija in praksa/Theory and Praxis in Slovenian as translated by ChatGPT-40.*)

Deliverable 4.3.2

Žagar, M. (2023). *Legitimate Multilevel Crisis Management from the Perspective of Human Rights, Minorities, and Non-Discrimination. Treatises and Documents/Razprave in gradivo*, No. 91, 5-24. ISSN 0354-0286.

Available at: <https://sciendo.com/article/10.2478/tdjes-20230012>,
<http://www.dlib.si/details/URN:NBN:SI:DOI:10.2478/tdjes-2023-0012>.

The Introductory Explanatory Note explains why the two articles (one in English and other in Slovenian) were written, their context and content. These articles present the WP4 research carried out by the dates of their submission, including the preliminary research data, results and findings of the qualitative field research. Based upon the in-depth open-ended interviews with respondents from different minority and distinct communities/groups, this qualitative field research studies their perceptions, views, opinions and assessments of the issues relevant for the legitimate crisis management in the context of human and minority rights, and the principle of non-discrimination. The Introductory Explanatory Note explains why the snow-ball sampling method was chosen to determine interviewees, the nature, process and expected results of the WP4 qualitative field research, as well the advantages, strengths, problems/weaknesses and shortcomings of such research and methodology.

In line with the strategic directions and policies of the EU and the European Commission, as well as most EU member states that promote collaboration and synergies between EU-funded and other research projects, particularly publically funded ones, in addition to the research data, results and findings of the WP4 qualitative research, in writing the article submitted in June 2024 also the research data, results, and findings of a fundamental research project on political participation of national minorities funded by the Slovenian Research Agency that are relevant for WP4 research are used.

In addition to these two articles, two more articles based on the research data, results, and findings of WP4 are planned to be submitted for publication in international scientific journals (likely in Croatia) by early to mid-2025, one by Ružica Jakešević and Siniša Tatalović, and one by Marta Zorko and Dana Luša.

Introductory Explanatory Note

Considering the recent communication with the coordinators of the LEGITIMULT project, the practice of other Work Packages (e.g., WP5 and their Deliverable 5.3, which consists of texts 5.3.1 and 5.3.2) that included multiple article texts prepared for publication in their Deliverable, as well as the comments on our Deliverable during the internal review of the LEGITIMULT project, I believe that this additional introductory explanation is necessary.

In the research projects I have participated in so far, coordinators, in cases where such a Deliverable was expected, required partners to submit already published articles in international scientific journals or proof that the articles being submitted had already been sent for review to international scientific journals by a specific deadline. This led to a certain misunderstanding because, in the case of the LEGITIMULT project, it was understood that by the Deliverable deadline, we needed to submit the text of the article or articles that were only prepared for submission to an international scientific journal. For this reason, our Deliverable 4.3 includes two texts that have already been submitted for publication: the first was submitted for publication in June 2024, and the second was published at the end of 2023, namely:

Deliverable 4.3.1

Žagar, M. (2024). Perceptions of Persons belonging to (Social) Minorities on the Legitimacy of Crisis Management during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Presentation of Field Research Results.

The text was submitted for publication in June 2024 to the independent scientific journal *Teorija in praksa/Theory and Practice*, a leading social science journal in Slovenia. The article was submitted in Slovenian (with the title: Percepcije pripadnikov različnih družbenih manjšin o legitimosti kriznega upravljanja v času pandemije covid-19: Predstavitev rezultatov terenskega raziskovanja). For this Deliverable (as agreed with the coordinators), an AI-translated English version of the article is included, in which some of the most obvious errors have been corrected. Additionally, missing segments were added in cases where parts of the text were not (fully) translated by ChatGPT-40.

Deliverable 4.3.2

Žagar, M. (2023). Legitimate Multilevel Crisis Management from the Perspective of Human Rights, Minorities, and Non-Discrimination. *Treatises and Documents/Razprave in gradivo*, No. 91, 5-24. ISSN 0354-0286.

Available at: <https://sciendo.com/article/10.2478/tdjes-20230012>,

<http://www.dlib.si/details/URN:NBN:SI>

DOI: 10.2478/tdjes-2023-0012.

The article was published at the end of 2023. The final revisions were made in November and early December 2023.

Regarding the provided texts, further clarification is needed. The document representing **Deliverable 4.3.1** was prepared in response to a question raised within the LEGITIMULT project about the potential issue of using the article **Deliverable 4.3.2**. Although this article was published in *Treatises and Documents*, an independent, indexed international scientific journal with a double-blind peer review process involving independent international reviewers, concerns were raised due to the fact that the founder of the journal is the Institute for Ethnic

Studies. Additionally, it was questioned whether it was appropriate for Deliverable 4.3 to include only research data, results, and findings up until the end of 2023.

To eliminate any doubts, I decided to write an additional scientific article that incorporates research data, results, and findings from WP4 up until June 2024. It also includes research data, results, and findings from a national fundamental/basic research project that I led, which aligns with the strategic directions and policies of the EU and the European Commission, as well as most EU member states. These strategies and policies promote collaboration and synergies between EU-funded and other research projects. I have actively contributed to shaping these policies as a researcher, reviewer (at the national level in several countries and for different EU projects), and as a former member of the Scientific Council of the Slovenian Research Agency.

The EU and member states aim to accelerate cooperation and synergies within the research sphere through this approach, encouraging broader use and sharing of obtained research data, results, and findings, and increasing the efficiency of publicly funded research.

Believing it would be unethical to publish two English-language articles with very similar content and some identical segments in different international journals, I submitted an additional new Slovenian-language article to another independent indexed scientific journal, *Teorija in praksa*, which is not associated with any LEGITIMULT partner. This article is currently under review. I chose to write the second article in Slovenian to contribute to the development of Slovene scholarly terminology.

In addition to the texts included in **Deliverable 4.3**, we are also preparing two more articles based on the research data, results, and findings from the qualitative field research conducted within WP4. We plan to submit these articles for publication in international scientific journals (likely in Croatia) by early to mid-2025. The authors of one article will be Ružica Jakešević and Siniša Tatalović, while the authors of the other will be Marta Zorko and Dana Luša. Thus, WP4 will fulfill its obligations within the LEGITIMULT project to a greater extent than initially planned (i.e., publishing one article in a scientific journal).

Additional publications, including a chapter in the LEGITIMULT project monograph, will provide a more detailed discussion of specific and broader societal contexts, as well as the topics (e.g., perceptions of gender issues, equality, principle of non-discrimination, etc.) that have not been addressed in the two articles already submitted for publication. It was only after systematizing and codifying the data presented in **Deliverable 4.4** that in the accompanying text we were able to offer a more comprehensive analysis and comment in more detail some of these issues, such as perceptions of the interviewees on how crisis management and individual crisis measures impacted their lives and rights, equality and the principle of non-discrimination, etc. Therefore, the two texts included in Deliverable 4.3 only address those aspects of these issues that could have been identified from the raw interviews (and/or their summaries) available at the time of submission.

As previously mentioned, both articles included in **Deliverable 4.3** and the two articles currently being prepared for publication are based on the research data, results, and findings from WP4's field research. This component of the LEGITIMULT project is unique because WP4 is the only work package conducting qualitative field research based on open-ended in-depth interviews, which is distinct in nature. This WP4 research complements the

predominantly quantitative and theoretical research and studies carried out by the other research-oriented work packages and serves as an addition to them. Through its qualitative research approach and the original scientific data obtained from fieldwork, WP4 can contribute to verifying, evaluating, and enhancing the interpretation of the research data, results, and findings of other (research-oriented) project work packages. Simultaneously, WP4 research data, results and findings indicating the perceptions and assessments of the interviewees coming from different minority and distinct communities/groups (including marginalized ones) regarding the topics relevant for the legitimate crisis management in the context of human and minority rights, and the principle of non-discrimination can serve as important inputs for the development of training and education contents and programs for specific target populations, as well as for the formulation of recommendations for practitioners and decision-makers at different levels.

The qualitative field research conducted by **WP4** through open in-depth interviews in selected countries (Austria, Croatia, Italy, and Slovenia) represents a long-term process that began in 2023 (starting with informal discussions and initial interviews) and is expected to conclude in the spring of 2025. As of now, the **WP4 database**, which was developed in October and prepared as **Deliverable 4.4** in November 2024, includes 48 interviews. The interviews contained in this database were conducted by WP4 team members from **FPZ** and **IES** (in collaboration with **SLORI**, whose associate carried out the interviews in Italy). Only once this WP4 database is formally published on the LEGITIMULT project's online system can it be formally cited in publications. Therefore, in the texts included in Deliverable 4.3, conference presentations and other materials produced by WP4 so far, only some of interviews used in their development and completion are mentioned or referenced.

To address some deficiencies of the snow-ball method detected so far, as explained in **Deliverable 4.4**, we plan to add a few additional interviews to the database by the spring of 2025, which we hope will be conducted not only by colleagues from **FPZ** and **IES**, but also by colleagues from **EURAC Research, Institute for Comparative Federalism**. With these interviews, we aim to include additional minority or specific communities (e.g., asylum seekers) that have not been included so far, increase the number of interviews in communities where only one or a few interviews were conducted, and improve, for instance, the gender balance of the interviewees. However, we have already indicated in the project proposal and at the Ljubljana 2024 LEGITIMULT Conference that using the snowball sampling method makes it very difficult, if not impossible, to ensure a balanced structure of interviewees.

Regarding the suggestion that interviews with the representatives of associations that work with asylum seekers and refugees should be included, it should be noted that the database presented in **Deliverable 4.4** already includes an interview with a representative of an association working with asylum seekers and refugees in Slovenia, and an additional interview is already scheduled with a representative of a similar association in Croatia.

However, despite all the weaknesses of the snowball sampling method, as has been explained several times and as established research practices in the study of various social minorities, particularly when researching small and specific communities, have shown, the snowball sampling method is generally appropriate and useful. It is often the most suitable method, and in some cases, when access to specific communities and their members is difficult, it is the only

feasible option. This method is especially useful in qualitative field research, such as that conducted by WP4.

It should also be emphasized that qualitative field research based on open in-depth interviews provides insight into the perceptions, attitudes, and opinions of individual interviewees. This is particularly valuable because it allows for the detection and recognition of internal pluralities and differences within even the smallest (minority) communities, which quantitative and other qualitative approaches and methods often do not capture. Such field-based qualitative research, as conducted by WP4, is not, however, most suitable for identifying general situations (since it captures respondents' opinions and perceptions about them). It is also important to exercise caution when generalizing its research data, results, and findings, as well as when making comparisons, since respondents' answers are typically influenced by specific temporal, social, historical, and value contexts.

For generalization, comparison, or comparative research, and the definition of general situations, quantitative methods and some other qualitative research approaches and methods are therefore more appropriate.

In quantitative research based on surveys and newly created and/or existing quantitative and/or quantified data, it is possible to create a database as soon as the required data has been collected. In contrast, creating qualitative databases from qualitative field research is a continuous process, which can take place throughout the duration of the research project (until its completion). The specific nature of this type of field qualitative research is that even individual interviews can serve as sources of research data and can, in a methodologically correct manner, be used in scientific publications. This is also the practice that we follow.

Thus, in the article published in *Treatises and Documents* at the end of 2023 (Deliverable 4.3.2), in addition to informal conversations with members of various minority communities and experts studying them, 19 interviews conducted up to that point as part of WP4 field research within the LEGITIMULT project were taken into account. In the article submitted for publication in *Teorija in praksa/Theory and Praxis*, 42 interviews conducted up to that point as part of WP4 field research were included, along with 16 interviews (in segments relevant to the LEGITIMULT project) conducted within the framework of the basic research project *Political Participation of National Minorities and Persons Belonging to Them: Comparative Study of Political Participation of Slovene Minorities in the Neighboring Countries of the Republic of Slovenia* (J5-3117) funded by ARRS (Slovenian National Research Agency)/ARIS (Slovenian National Research and Innovation Agency). Therefore, the statement in Deliverable 4.3.1 that 58 interviews were considered in writing the article is correct.

Regarding the interviews conducted as part of WP4 field research, I should add that when writing the article, I had access to the full interview for some of the conducted interviews, while for others, I only had brief summaries. To avoid incorrect use/citation and misinterpretation of the interviews, as well as errors in their interpretation, I sent the draft of the article to the researchers from Ljubljana and Zagreb, whose interviews I directly used in writing the article, for review before submitting it for publication. I took into account all the corrections, suggestions, and comments I received in preparing the version of the text that was submitted for publication. It is also important to note that these researchers can read and understand the Slovenian texts.

I emphasize that, as the author, by including also data, results and findings of another (in this case basic national) research project, I took into account the aforementioned European and national strategic guidelines and policies in the field of research and science, which encourage cooperation and synergies between various European (EU) and national, as well as other research projects, especially those (co-)financed by public funds. The fact that, in addition to the research data, results, and findings from the qualitative field research conducted within WP4 of the LEGITIMULT project, research data, results, and findings from the mentioned research project were also used, enriches and enhances both the results and their value, thus contributing to the overall quality of the research. Therefore, this fact should be regarded as a special added value that is certainly in the public interest. Strictly separating and dividing the results of research projects is therefore illogical and undesirable. However, it is, of course, essential that sources and projects are correctly cited in such cases, which has been done in the case of Deliverables 4.3.1 and 4.3.2.

To the greatest extent possible—taking into account the explanations and justifications in this introductory clarification, as well as the corrections, remarks, and comments provided by the reviewers during the peer-review process of the international scientific journal—I will incorporate the comments and feedback from both internal and external reviewers of the LEGITIMULT project in preparing the final version of the article for publication in *Teorija in praksa*.

Perceptions of Persons belonging to (Social) Minorities on the Legitimacy of Crisis Management during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Presentation of Field Research Results

Note:

This is a translation of the article that was originally written in Slovene and submitted for publication in *Theory and Practice*.

Translated by:

ChatGPT-40
Google translate
On 19.9.2024

Some factual inconsistencies, obvious mistakes and gaps in the AI translated text (where certain parts of the original text were not translated) were corrected by the author.

Article title:

Perceptions of Persons belonging to (Social) Minorities on the Legitimacy of Crisis Management during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Presentation of Field Research Results

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STATEMENT:

I declare that the text I am submitting for publication in *Theory and Practice* has not yet been published and is not being prepared for publication in any other scientific journal or monograph.

prof. dr. Mitja Žagar

Ljubljana, 17 June 2024

Project funded by

Perceptions of Persons belonging to (Social) Minorities on the Legitimacy of Crisis Management during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Presentation of Field Research Results¹

ABSTRACT:

The article presents a brief overview of the literature, the conceptual and methodological framework, and the initial findings of field research on the perceptions and attitudes of persons belonging to social/national/ethnic/linguistic minorities regarding the COVID-19 pandemic and crisis management, focusing on the legitimacy of crisis management and measures, their impact on human rights, and the implementation of the principle of non-discrimination, as well as on the situation, status, rights, protection, inclusion, and integration of minorities. Using open-ended in-depth interviews, the research in Austria, Croatia, Italy, Hungary, and Slovenia (within projects of ARRS/ARIS and Horizon Europe LEGITMULT project) was conducted from summer 2021 to June 2024.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19 pandemic; crisis management and measures; social minorities and their members; national/ethnic/linguistic minorities; legitimacy of crisis management

¹ The paper presents the initial results of the field research of the LEGITMULT project on legitimate crisis management in multi-level systems, funded by the European Union (Horizon Europe Programme Call HORIZON-CL2-2021-DEMOCRACY-91, GA No. 101051550) and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), as well as the research program *Minority and Ethnic Studies and the Slovenian National Question* (P5-0081) and the basic research project *Political Participation of National Minorities and Their Members: A Comparative Study of the Political Participation of Slovenian Communities in the Neighboring Countries of the Republic of Slovenia* (J5-3117), both funded by ARRS/ARIS.

1. Introduction

Topics related to the SARS-CoV-2 virus, the COVID-19 pandemic, and the management of this (global) crisis dominated the news, publications, and comments in mass and online media, as well as professional and scientific publications in medicine and the natural sciences, but also in engineering, social sciences, and humanities, during the 2020-2023 period. The pandemic and crisis management affected all individuals, groups, communities, environments, and societies, influencing their lives on all levels (from local communities to the global scale). National, European, and international research projects, along with professional and scientific publications, have also focused on the specific circumstances, impacts, significance, and consequences of the crisis and crisis management on various social minorities, including national, ethnic, and linguistic minorities (e.g., Žagar 2020; 2021; 2023a; 2023b). However, there are no publications addressing the perceptions and attitudes of members of these minorities regarding the COVID-19 pandemic, the crisis, and crisis management, as well as their effects on minority communities and their members, which represent their views on the legitimacy of crisis management based on field research conducted in various countries.

This paper fills that gap. It presents the results of field research from the basic research project ARRS/ARIS "Political Participation of National Minorities and Their Members: A Comparative Study of the Political Participation of Slovenian Communities in the Neighbouring Countries of the Republic of Slovenia" (J5-3117)² and the initial findings from field research on the perceptions and attitudes of members of various social minorities as part of Work Package 4 (DS4/WP4) on legitimate multi-level crisis management from the perspective of human rights, minorities, and non-discrimination. This research is coordinated by the Institute for Ethnic Studies (INV) as part of the Horizon Europe LEGITMULT project on legitimate crisis management in multi-level systems³. Between summer 2021 and June 2024, several informal discussions and 58 open in-depth interviews were conducted with members of various social minorities in Austria, Italy, and Slovenia, as well as in Croatia and Hungary.⁴ Although the proposal for the basic research project, prepared before the COVID-19 pandemic, did not mention the pandemic, the associated crisis, or crisis management, the very first interviews revealed that these topics would be important and repeatedly mentioned by respondents, elected representatives of these minorities, due to their impact on the lives and status of Slovenian minorities in neighbouring countries. As a result, questions related to these topics were included in the open in-depth interviews and asked to all twenty interviewees. At the beginning of WP4 field research within the LEGITMULT project, sixteen interviewees from Austria and Italy, who were part of the basic research project, were also included among the first interviewees for this European project, and both interviews were conducted with them. For the LEGITMULT project, these interviewees, using the "snowball" method, also proposed

² Refer to <http://www.inv.si/Dokumenti/dokumenti.aspx?iddoc=1009&idmenu1=19&lang=slo>

³ Refer to LEGITMULT – Legitimate crisis governance in multilevel systems, a project funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe Programme Call HORIZON-CL2-2021-DEMOCRACY-91, GA No. 101051550 and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). <https://legitimult.eu/>

⁴ The interviews were and will be conducted by colleagues of the Institute for Ethnic Issues, Dr. Romana Bešter, Dr. Danijel Grafenauer, Dr. Boris Jesih, Prof. Dr. Matjaž Klemenčič, Dr. Janez Pirc and Dr. Barbara Riman, Dr. Zaira Vidau, associate of the Slovenian Research Institute (SLORI) from Trieste, associate of the Slovenian Scientific Institute (SZI) from Klagenfurt, Prof. Dr. Valentin Sima, colleagues of the Faculty of Political Sciences of the University of Zagreb (FPZ SZG) Prof. Dr. Ružica Jakešević, Prof. Dr. Đana Luša, Prof. Dr. Siniša Tatalović and Prof. Dr. Marta Zorko and colleagues of the Eurac Research, Institute for Comparative Federalism (EURAC Research) from Bolzano/Bozen Dr. Elisabeth Alber and Martina Gianola.

potential additional interviewees from their minority and other minority communities in Austria, Croatia, Italy, and Slovenia. Interviews as part of WP4 will continue until spring 2025, so the number of interviews will increase. In addition to members of the Slovenian minority, the interviewees in Croatia include members of the Italian, Hungarian, Roma, Slovak, and Serbian minorities (mainly representatives of minorities at the local, county, and national levels, as well as officials from minority organizations), members of the LGBTIQ+ community, and representatives of state institutions, local and regional governments, and associations that collaborate with these communities. In Italy, interviewees include members of the Slovenian minority, while the interviews with the German minority and members of the border community in South Tyrol, and with migrants and asylum seekers are also planned. In Slovenia, the interviewees include members of the Italian and Hungarian national minorities, the Roma community, and immigrant communities. We also plan to conduct interviews with representatives of state institutions and local governments that collaborate with them. In Croatia and Slovenia, it is not possible to conduct interviews on the perceptions of the COVID-19 crisis and crisis management in these countries with migrants and asylum seekers, as migrants in these transit countries typically stay for only a short period (a few days, weeks, or months) before moving on. As a result, nearly all migrants and asylum seekers who were in these countries during the crisis have already left.

The goal of the presented field research is to identify the perceptions and attitudes of members of various social minorities (and specific communities) regarding the COVID-19 pandemic, the crisis, and crisis management during the pandemic from the perspective of the legitimacy of crisis management and measures, their impact on human rights and freedoms, and the situation, status, rights, protection, inclusion, and integration of minorities (theirs and others). This paper examines two complex working hypotheses: (1) crisis management strategies, processes, policies, and measures in pluralistic and diverse societies affect everyone in these environments, but typically have a more significant impact on various minorities and marginalized communities/groups and their members; (2) appropriate, timely, and comprehensive crisis communication, including in minority languages, as well as formal and actual participation (or at least symbolic inclusion) of minorities and their members (primarily their formal/informal representatives) in the development, adoption, and implementation of crisis management processes, strategies, policies, and measures, improve the legitimacy and effectiveness of crisis management.

2. Conceptual framework, brief literature review and methodological approach

The phenomena, such as complex, dynamic, internally plural and diverse societies, local communities and other levels of local self-government, regions and federal units in federations, states and their (international) integration, as well as the international community are complex and dynamic (social) processes. The international community is a community of states, fundamental subjects of international law, relations and cooperation. States as specific forms of social organization and systems of regulation and management of social relations and processes within their borders are defined as fundamental units of social science study and comparison. In the international community, countries are interconnected and interdependent, so they can only be considered as independent variables in research only conditionally. This also applies to the largest, strongest and most influential countries that represent global or regional (great) powers. The covid-19 pandemic has also confirmed that this is true.

Organization, regulation and management in modern societies and countries are complex dynamic multi-level processes that can be successful if all relevant levels of organization, decision-making and management work and participate in them successfully and in a coordinated manner. As the crisis related to the covid-19 pandemic has confirmed, this also applies to crisis management. Therefore, when researching the perceptions and attitudes of members of social minorities about the success and legitimacy of crisis management during the covid-19 pandemic in their environment, taking into account the consequences and impact of crisis management on the position, rights, inclusion and integration of their communities, we pay special attention to their interpretations of the role, influence, cooperation and performance of individual levels of government that participated in crisis management.

Right at the beginning of the covid-19 pandemic, the first scientific publications about the SARS-CoV-2 virus, the covid-19 disease and the covid-19 pandemic appeared, especially in the natural sciences and medicine, the number of which was growing rapidly. (e.g. Nature; Science; The Lancet; Wiley Online Library; WoS) The covid-19 pandemic and the related crisis management have radically changed the lives of people and societies globally and in every local environment. Taking into account their (especially social and economic) influence, resonance and consequences, it is not surprising that researchers from practically all sciences, disciplines and fields immediately began to deal with these topics. Due to the enormous number and scope of professional and scientific publications on the SARS-CoV-2 virus, the covid-19 pandemic, related crises and crisis management, this literature review focuses on a few fundamental themes, concepts and contexts that provide starting points for understanding the impact and the consequences of crisis management for various social minorities, the rights and protection of minorities, their situation and position, inclusion, participation and integration, and for the understanding and interpretation of the perceptions and attitudes of members of these communities, which are studied by the presented projects. These topics include:

- legitimacy (e.g. Beetham 2012; Buchanan 2002; Caby & Frehen 2021; De Fine Licht et al. 2014; Esaiasson et al. 2012; Jackson et al. 2012);
- approaches, concepts, strategies, policies and measures of crisis management in general and during the covid-19 pandemic (e.g. Ansel et al. 2010; Christensen et al. 2016; Christensen & Ma 2021; Rodríguez et al. 2018);
- the roles of branches of government and especially legislation in crisis management processes (e.g. Bolleyer & Salát 2021; Chaplin 2020; Petrov 2020); and
- democracy, inclusion, integration and participation of citizens and their perceptions of crisis management, its impacts and consequences (e.g. Alsan et al. 2020/2023, Bohle et al. 2022; Cronert 2022; Edgell et al. 2021; Engler et al. 2021; Guasti & Liese 2021; Maerz et al. 2021).

The literature review, taking into account the goals, design and topics of both projects and the conducted field research, focuses on issues of proportionality and legitimacy of crisis management and individual measures, human rights, the situation, rights and protection of various minorities and their inclusion and integration, equal rights, equality, and realization/implementation of the principle (and policies) of non-discrimination. From the point of view of (social) minorities and their members, their inclusion and integration and the consequences that crisis management and measures have had on their life, inclusion and integration, considering their impacts and consequences, this literature review indicates the importance of the repressive and restrictive measures such as restrictions and temporary suspension of rights, restrictions on movement are important, closures of society (lockdowns),

local and national borders, school closures and (longer) distance learning, as well as limited access to health and other public services reported by the media. (e.g. 24ur.com; BBC News; CNBC News; DW; MMC, etc.) The media and commentators assessed that such measures markedly disproportionately affect (social) minorities and their members, and especially marginalized individuals and groups at the economic and social bottom, which are already largely excluded. However, such media reports and comments as well as public expressions of dissatisfaction (including mass protests) did not significantly affect the processes of crisis management and the (especially executive) authorities in various environments, which were key in the formulation, adoption and implementation of crisis strategies, policies and measures. The authorities that adopted crisis policies and decisions explained and justified their behaviour and exclusion of other actors and the public from the decision-making process by the urgency and criticality of the crisis situation. They stressed that the exceptional situation demands exceptional and immediate action in order to prevent the worst consequences. In this way, they responded to critics who - often rightly - claimed that at least some of the restrictive and repressive crisis measures and interventions in human rights, such as the suspension of individual human rights, closures and restrictions on movement, were not proportionate. The authorities argued that the urgency of action left no time for wider debate and consultation, and in particular no time for protracted, uncertain and possibly ineffective inclusive democratic processes. Even in cases where the courts later found the illegality and unconstitutionality of individual (especially repressive) policies and measures⁵, the authorities and decision-makers who made and implemented these decisions insisted on their explanations and added that they would have acted the same way in similar situations. They believe that their curtailment of democracy, inclusion and human rights was necessary and worth the price. In doing so, they referred to the experience of the "war on terror", which showed that people are willing to accept temporary restrictions on human rights and (fundamental) freedoms in exchange for promises of better security and protection, even if these are false. Moreover, it has been shown that the "silent" majority is ready to accept such restrictions even if they become permanent or at least very long-lasting. (Žagar 2020; 2023a; 2023b)

Among the first scientific publications on the covid-19 pandemic, relevant from the point of view of national and other social minorities and their members, we mention the 85th thematic issue of the journal *Razprave in gradivo* (2020) with eleven contributions that deal with the direct impact of the pandemic on various areas of the lives of national minorities and the first consequences of the pandemic felt by minority communities, the extensive scientific monograph *The world has become different: The impact of covid-19 on ethnic minorities and the border area in Slovenia and neighbouring countries*, edited by Katalin Munda Hirnök and Sonja Novak-Lukanovič (2021), and a study on the impact and consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on linguistic minorities and border communities in South Tyrol (Alber et al. 2021).

⁵ For example, when the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Slovenia (2021) assessed the constitutionality of points 2 and 3 of the first paragraph of Article 39 of the Infectious Diseases Act (ZNB), it found that the provisions were inconsistent with the second paragraph of Article 32 and the third paragraph of Article 42 of the Constitution of the Republic of Slovenia, but in order to protect people's health and life, it decided that they can use these provisions until the discrepancy is resolved. At the same time, it concluded that even the Government's decrees, adopted on the basis of the mentioned legal provisions, are not in accordance with the constitution, and therefore they are annulled. (Decision of the Constitutional Court No. U-I-79/20 of 13/05/2021.) Similarly, the Italian Constitutional Court annulled important parts of the special law on the management of the covid-19 pandemic, which was adopted by the regional parliament of South Tyrol.

The report of the Croatian Ombudsman on the state of human rights and equality in the country in 2021 (Pučka pravobraniteljica 2022a) notes that, as in other countries, human rights and (fundamental) freedoms, including the rights of minorities, were among the first victims of crises and crisis management. Her recommendations for better resilience to future crises, based on assessments of the impact of the covid-19 pandemic on human rights and equality (Pučka pravobraniteljica 2022b), confirm such a conclusion. The adoption and enforcement of restrictive, repressive and often disproportionate crisis measures, restrictions and (temporary!?) suspension of human rights and freedoms, which, as determined by the courts, represent a violation of human rights and democratic principles, cannot be considered as legitimate and democratic crisis management (Huffstetler et al. 2021; Žagar 2021).

The covid-19 pandemic has exposed and highlighted existing inequalities, such as the often long-standing social, economic, ethnic and racial inequalities in modern societies. At the same time, it created new inequalities (Katikireddi et al. 2021; Platt & Warwick 2020). Already economically and socially disadvantaged individuals, including members of ethnic, racial and other minorities, including migrants, refugees and other marginalized individuals and groups, have become even more vulnerable and more exposed to infection than others during the pandemic, their access to public healthcare and other services was even more difficult and worse (also compared to the rest of the population); in addition, their pre-existing diseases and (medical) conditions (e.g. diabetes, obesity, hypertension, cardiovascular problems, etc.) worsened. Compared to the rest of the population, data show that they often suffered excess mortality (Kumar et al. 2021; OECD 2022).

The negative experiences, impacts and consequences of the covid-19 pandemic and crisis management confirm that in order to increase resilience to similar crises and to better face crises in the future, all environments must prepare plans and measures for better resilience and recovery at all levels. These plans and measures must improve access to public services for all residents, ensure equal access, reduce digital and other differences, and in all areas promote the inclusion, equality and equity of all individuals, regardless of gender, ethnicity or any other personal characteristic and status, groups and communities. In addition to ensuring equal inclusion and integration, these plans and measures must also prevent all types of violence. Among individuals and groups, these plans and measures must pay special attention to women, children and young people, the elderly, persons with disabilities, individuals in precarious work and social situations, the homeless and various social minorities, including national, ethnic, linguistic and religious minorities, the community LGBTQIA+ and other marginalized groups and individuals (FRA 2022a; 2022b; UN 2020).

For members of national, ethnic and linguistic minorities and these communities, the (use) of minority and regional languages in public communication in general and also in crisis management is key, as confirmed by an online survey conducted between March and June 2020 in EU member states among members of the federal Union of European National Minorities (FUEN). The public use of the mother tongue, information, communication, public services and crisis instructions in minority languages contribute to better inclusion of minorities and improve the efficiency, legitimacy and democracy of crisis management. However, the pandemic and restrictive measures are likely to have a longer-term impact on the ethnic vitality of minorities. Among the restrictive crisis measures, minorities and border communities were particularly affected by the closing of state borders, which halted daily cross-border contacts, cooperation and migration, the closure of minority and/or bilingual schools, the cancellation of traditional

minority events and events. Minorities who have the support of the states of ethnic origin (kin states), who are well internally organized and connected, who are integrated into the wider social environment, who have access to information technology, communication and institutional infrastructure for organizing alternative online communities, responded better to the crisis, restrictive and repressive measures and hybrid activities and are able to adapt to a changed situation, such as Slovenian minority in Austria. (FUEN 2020; Grafenauer and Jesih 2020; Jurić Pahor 2020)

The pandemic and crisis management further deepened the long-term exclusion, poverty and discrimination of the Roma, Europe's largest and most marginalized ethnic minority. Inadequate dwellings without potable and sanitary water and adequate sanitary facilities often make it impossible for Roma to implement preventive and other public health measures, and their access to health services has also been made more difficult. Exposed to exclusionary and often racist media coverage and public discourse, which portrayed the Roma as a collective threat to public health in Bulgaria, Slovakia, Romania and some other countries, they were in some environments victims of disproportionately repressive crisis measures that particularly affected Roma settlements. In Slovenia and across Europe, Roma students were more affected than others by the closure of schools and long-term distance education, as they often did not have adequate digital access and technical equipment. Therefore, their educational success further deteriorated, and their exclusion and difficulties in establishing contact and cooperation between teachers, Roma students and their parents increased. (Bešter and Pirc 2020; FRA 2020b; Matache and Bhabha 2020).

Most of the mentioned authors note that the democracy and legitimacy of crisis management contribute to its better efficiency. They believe that exclusionary, restrictive and repressive crisis management with the dominance of the executive power in social environments has a negative impact on democracy and strengthens populism and illiberal democracy, which during the pandemic was expressed in the strengthening of exclusion, discrimination, aggressive nationalism, racism and xenophobia (e.g. Elias et al. 2021).

Aware that there are no ideal approaches and methods in the social sciences and humanities for the study of complex, dynamic and constantly changing (social) phenomena and concepts, as well as perceptions and attitudes about them, we - in accordance with the approach of methodological pluralism, which has proven to be useful in the field of ethnic studies (e.g. Della Porta and Keating 2008) – decided on a quantitative approach using open-ended in-depth interviews. The review of the literature, the previous research and its results, the application of the mentioned research projects and informal conversations with members of various minority communities, with which we checked some starting points and concepts, represented the substantive and methodological starting points for formulating questions for open in-depth interviews that establish perceptions and attitudes interviewees, members of various minorities, about the covid-19 pandemic and crisis and crisis management from the point of view of the legitimacy of crisis management and measures, their impact on human and minority rights, on the situation, position, protection, inclusion and integration of their (and other) minorities. Based on past experience, that members and especially representatives of various minorities often want their name, work, position in the minority community and their views to be visible in research, research results and publications resulting from them, we enable them to do so, in accordance with rules and standards of ethical research. Each interviewee decides if they want their interview to be anonymized or give their consent that the interview is not anonymized and

that the identity and data provided in the research are visible and public. Taking into account the specifics of researching minority communities and topics, the first interviewees were selected based on existing contacts and information about individual minority communities. A snowball approach was used to select additional interviewees and minority communities. We tried to include at least three interviewees from each minority community in order to perceive the internal diversity of these communities and the existence of different perceptions and attitudes. When this is not possible, we also conducted an interview with only one member of a specific minority community, because we judged that this is valuable for detecting perceptions and attitudes in these communities and for evaluating and interpreting the obtained data and research results.

In the interviews, interviewees are asked about their perceptions, assessments and attitudes towards: relations between the majority and minorities and between minorities during the pandemic; inclusion and integration of their minority and its members; crisis management and measures - taking into account their impact on human rights, protection of minorities and discrimination; efficiency, effectiveness, democracy and legitimacy of crisis management and measures; the impact and consequences of crisis management and measures for their community and its members in general and in comparison with the majority and other minorities; possible proposals and changes that would improve crisis management, increase its democracy and legitimacy, reduce the restrictiveness and repressiveness of crisis measures that limit human rights and freedoms, such as restricting movement, closing borders and schools; and the legitimacy of authorities, crisis management and measures at individual levels. We also ask them about their trust in the authorities at individual levels and about proposals for improving the inclusion and participation of minorities and their members in crisis management processes at all levels of decision-making.

Informal conversations with members and activists of various minorities (e.g. national, ethnic and linguistic minorities, migrants, etc.) and individuals dealing with minority issues (e.g. representatives of various institutions and societies, researchers) are considered a useful complement to other research approaches and methods. In informal conversations we talked about terminology and concepts, about the broader context of crisis management and social inclusion of minorities in preparation for field research and during its implementation. They helped to check the terminology and concepts used and to explain them better to the interviewees. They draw attention to the specific position and characteristics of the interviewees (e.g. education, status, inclusion and integration), the specificity of minority and other studied communities, their internal plurality and diversity. Therefore, before starting the interviews, we first ask the interviewees to explain to us their (often very different) understanding of individual terms and concepts, before we present to them how we use them within the framework of the two projects.

We know from experience that interviewees often perceive interviews as formal communication that demands socially correct behavior and answers, which can influence their answers, expressed perceptions and attitudes. In informal communication, as a rule, participants are more relaxed and express what they do not want to say in formal communication. Therefore, informal interviews are also a supplement to interviews and help in evaluating and interpreting the interviewees' answers.

3. Presentation of some findings of field research

When presenting the results of the field research and their interpretation, we point out that about a third of the interlocutors in informal conversations and interviewees mention at the beginning of the conversation or interview and/or when answering individual questions that since the peak of the covid-19 pandemic, the crisis and individual restrictive and repressive measures it's been a while. Therefore, sometimes they do not remember details and are not sure about the reliability of their memory. The interlocutors agree that formal and informal inclusion in (democratic) decision-making processes, the participation of members of minorities, their representatives and (ad)consultative bodies in which they participate, as well as communication in minority languages contribute to democracy, greater legitimacy and effectiveness of crisis management, decisions and measures. They recommend decision-makers to take into account existing social plurality and diversity, specific situations, needs and interests of different minorities, and the diversity and existence of different interests within minorities.

Members of national/ethnic/linguistic minorities believe that the authorities (at least) in the areas where these minorities live, in everyday life and especially in crisis situations, must provide information, instructions and communication also in the languages of these minorities. This is not only about ensuring the rights and protection of minorities and their members in democracies in principle, but such practice improves the efficiency and quality and increases the legitimacy of (social and political) decision-making, including crisis management and measures. This is particularly important when not all members of these minorities have a good understanding of the official/majority language.

The interviewees note that in the initial stages of pandemics and crises, it is difficult or impossible to involve various actors in decision-making, as urgent decisions and crisis measures must be taken as soon as possible to protect lives, public health and safety. However, they recommend that decision-makers at least consult relevant actors, including members and especially representatives of minority and marginalized communities, as soon as possible. Whenever possible, they should be included in decision-making. They believe that crisis decisions and measures must also take into account the specific situations, needs and interests of minority, specific and marginalized communities and persons with special needs in individual environments. In order to empower them for full inclusion, cooperation/participation and integration in the environments where they live, all residents and communities must be engaged in lifelong civic education and education for inclusive societies.

In informal discussions and interviews, members of minorities emphasize that democratic societies must guarantee the highest standards of human rights and (fundamental) freedoms. Minority rights (and minority protection based on them) are human rights and freedoms. The principles of equal rights, equality and non-discrimination should equally guarantee rights and freedoms to all and prevent intentional or unintentional, direct or indirect discrimination on the basis of race, sex, birth, any personal characteristic, national/ethnic or social origin and affiliation and/or class, language, religion, sexual orientation, beliefs and political or other opinions and values. They believe that the level of inclusion, integration, protection and cooperation or the participation of persons, members and representatives of various specific, minority and/or marginalized communities, and these communities as collective subjects, a key indicator of the development and realization of democracy in individual environments. When designing, regulating and enforcing the protection of minorities and when preventing all forms

of discrimination, all environments must take into account the specific situations, needs and interests of each community and its members, which means that they must treat different situations and contexts differently. They emphasize that individual (especially general) policies do not affect all individuals and communities living in a particular environment in the same way, therefore they note that minorities and marginalized communities and their members are often disproportionately (mostly more) affected. They believe that the covid-19 pandemic, crisis management and (especially restrictive and repressive) measures have most affected marginalized, more isolated and less integrated communities, such as Roma and the LGBTIQ+ community, and their members, who have been more discriminated against than the majority population, as well as other minorities and their members. Individuals who identify with several minorities and/or marginalized communities (e.g. ethnic/national minority, LGBTIQ+, unemployed, poor and socially disadvantaged, etc.) have been particularly exposed to discrimination.

Preliminary analyzes show that perceptions and attitudes about the situation and position of individual minorities and other specific, especially marginalized communities and their members during the covid-19 pandemic, about the effectiveness and legitimacy of crisis management and measures, as well as about the impact and consequences of crisis management and individual (especially restrictive and repressive) measures for these communities and their members differ (significantly). It is about specific perceptions and interpretations of individuals not only between different communities, but also within individual communities. This confirms the (internal) complexity, dynamism, plurality and diversity of these communities and explains why caution is needed when comparing and especially when interpreting and generalizing findings. Informal conversations and interviews show that interlocutors perceive crisis management as exclusionary, centralized and undemocratic. However, they are not sure whether less centralized and more inclusive practices, which would otherwise increase the legitimacy of crisis management, would be more successful. They estimate that initially and at the national level, meritocratic, centralized, exclusive and undemocratic crisis management with the enforcement of restrictive and also repressive measures is more effective, justified and even necessary in order to prevent the worst consequences. At the local and regional level and later in the crisis, a more inclusive crisis management, in which representatives of various minority communities would also participate, would be welcome, more legitimate and probably more successful.

Agreeing that more inclusion, participation and democracy and taking into account the specific situations, rights, (social, health, educational, cultural and economic) needs and interests of different, minority and/or marginalized communities and their members would improve the legitimacy, efficiency and effectiveness of the crisis management and measures, especially at the regional and local level, emphasize that all crisis policies and measures should have clear legal foundations that define the nature, scope, content and duration of the measures, enable their flexibility and ensure better predictability.

Among the restrictive and repressive measures, the interviewees cited as particularly problematic the restriction and/or temporary suspension of individual human rights and freedoms, restriction of movement and lockdowns, closing of state borders, closing of schools and long-term distance education. Interviewees from national/ethnic/linguistic minorities and border communities point out that movement restrictions, lockdowns, curfews and closures of international borders have interrupted their cross-border cooperation and mobility, connections

with related communities and countries, and people on the other side of borders. These measures have at least temporarily stopped and/or made the cultural, sports and social life of minorities, their educational activities and training programs significantly more difficult. Over time, canceled (social, cultural and educational) mass events and traditional programs, important for the preservation, promotion and development of their culture, identity, way of life and their communities, have at least to a certain extent been replaced by online activities. However, they note that these measures have affected the vitality of minority communities. Although they agree that school closures and remote learning during the covid-19 pandemic have affected everyone, they note that pupils, students and students from minority and/or marginalized communities have felt these restrictions more than the rest of the population.

During the pandemic in Croatia and Slovenia, members of isolated and marginalized communities such as the Roma, often unemployed and socially threatened, had additional problems accessing health and other public services, such as distance education, which were accessible digitally. Since they often did not have IT equipment, access to the Internet and important information, the necessary knowledge and skills, they could not make an appointment with a doctor and it was more difficult to get vaccinations. Poor living conditions and inadequate communal infrastructure made personal hygiene and the implementation of preventive measures difficult. Distance education was even more difficult for Roma students, who did not even have basic conditions at home, than for their classmates. Members of the LGBTIQ+ community in Croatia, who before the pandemic, due to negative attitudes in society, legislation and discrimination, were provided medical services abroad, were prevented from doing so during the pandemic and border closures. Their access to health services was therefore made more difficult, and the feeling of threat and pressure on them increased.

4. Concluding thoughts

As limited as it is, the article fills a void identified by a review of the professional and scientific literature. It offers a brief review of the literature and a discussion of some conceptual and methodological issues of researching the perceptions and attitudes of members of social minorities and specific communities about the covid-19 pandemic, the crisis and crisis management during the pandemic from the point of view of the legitimacy of crisis management and measures, their impact on human rights and freedoms, on the situation, position, rights, protection, inclusion and integration of (their own and other) minorities. It presents some key findings and results of field research conducted using open in-depth interviews in the neighboring countries of Austria, Croatia, Italy, Hungary and Slovenia. The presented allows us to confirm the assumptions that we have formulated as complex (working) hypotheses. We find that crisis management strategies, processes, policies and measures in plural and diverse societies affect everyone in these environments, but as a rule, different minorities and marginalized communities/groups and their members are affected more than the rest of the population. Interviews and informal conversations also confirmed that adequate, timely and comprehensive crisis communication also in the language of minorities and formal and actual participation or at least symbolic inclusion of minorities and their members (especially their formal/informal representatives) in the design, acceptance and implementation crisis management processes, strategies, policies and measures improve the legitimacy and effectiveness of crisis management.

Taking into account the experience of the covid-19 pandemic, the opinions and suggestions of the interviewees, as well as the findings and recommendations formulated in the framework of the presented research projects, are useful for ensuring better resilience of plural and internally diverse societies and more democratic, legitimate, quality and effective crisis management in dealing with future crises. Therefore, it is important to continue researching these topics.

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Legitimate Multilevel Crisis Management from the Perspective of Human Rights, Minorities, and Non-Discrimination

The COVID-19 pandemic has dominated media and scholarly literature since 2020. The impact(s) of crisis management on democracy, legitimacy, human rights, minorities, marginalized groups, and persons belonging to them are mentioned but seldom the main focus. From the perspective of human rights, protection of minorities, and the principle of non-discrimination in multilevel systems in Europe, the paper discusses certain conceptual, terminological, and methodological problems in studying such complex dynamic phenomena and argues that qualitative approaches might be the most suitable for studying the perceptions of persons belonging to diverse minorities on democracy and the legitimacy of crisis management and governance.

Keywords: crisis management, inclusion, multilevel governance, social minorities and persons belonging to them, human and minority rights, non-discrimination, LEGITIMULT project.

Legitimnost večnivojskega kriznega upravljanja z vidika človekovih pravic, manjšin in nediskriminacije

Mediji in znanstvena literatura od leta 2020 omenjajo vplive kriznega upravljanja med pandemijo covid-19 na demokracijo, legitimnost, človekove pravice, manjšine in marginalizirane skupine ter njihove pripadnike, a jih redko podrobneje obravnavajo. Članek obravnava nekatera konceptualna, terminološka in metodološka vprašanja proučevanja teh kompleksnih dinamičnih pojavov z vidika človekovih pravic, varstva manjšin in nediskriminacije v evropskih večnivojskih sistemih. Ugotavlja, da so kvalitativni pristopi najprimernejši za proučevanje percepcij pripadnikov manjšin glede demokratičnosti in legitimnosti kriznega upravljanja.

Ključne besede: *krizno upravljanje, vključevanje, večnivojsko upravljanje, družbene manjšine in njihovi pripadniki, človekove pravice in pravice manjšin, nediskriminacija, projekt LEGITIMULT.*

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1. Introduction

In recent years, the SARS-CoV-2 virus, the COVID-19 pandemic, and pandemic related crisis management have been omnipresent topics in media and public discourse. They also dominate scholarly literature and publications in almost all disciplines and fields, including the social sciences and humanities (e.g., Žagar 2020; 2023). This paper discusses specific issues, concepts, dimensions, and contexts that are often overlooked.

When observed from the perspective of multilevel governance (MLG) and considering the very nature and complexity of the process(es), crisis management is a complex multilevel process that requires cooperation and coordination in various levels of government and authorities effected by and involved in it. In global crises, such as the COVID-19 pandemic that shook the very foundations of contemporary societies and our traditional way(s) of life, crisis management processes resulted in specific crisis strategies, policies, decisions and measures, as well as in their implementation that impacted populations, individuals, distinct groups, and (particularly minority and border) communities in various societies and environments. Restrictive and/or repressive crisis policies and measures and their implementation impacted them profoundly. Considering the responsibilities, competences, tasks, relations, and cooperation of governments and authorities at all levels, the LEGITIMULT project on the legitimacy of COVID-19 related crisis management and measures in diverse environmentsⁱ studies and compares COVID-19 crisis management process(es), decision making and measures, and their effects and consequences in European countries, more precisely in 31 European democracies (EU-27, plus Switzerland, Norway, Iceland, and the UK) from the perspective of various actors, democracy, and the legitimacy of crisis management and governance.

In this context, the LEGITIMULT projectⁱⁱ examines various impacts and consequences of COVID-19 related crisis management in diverse environments on the human rights, status, situation, rights, and protection of minorities, and the principle of non-discrimination. Based on the review of literature studying the impact of COVID-19 measures on different societal groups and the effects of those measures, multilevel governance institutions and their intergovernmental relations (MLG IGR) concerning human and minority rights, the project and paper address two research questions: Which conditions, circumstances, policies, measures, and actions can contribute to more democratic and legitimate crisis management and governance? How can the inclusion and participation of diverse social actors, including (social) minorities,ⁱⁱⁱ in crisis management processes and decision-making be improved, thereby contributing to their legitimacy?

Taking these questions into account, this paper and the Work Package (WP4) on legitimate crisis governance in the context of human rights, minority rights, and the principle of non-discrimination test four (working) hypotheses.

Two general hypotheses are: (H1) In different ways, crisis management processes related to the COVID-19 pandemic, adopted and executed strategies, policies, and measures, particularly restrictive and/or repressive ones that limited and/or suspended certain human rights, impact all individuals, communities, groups, associations, organisations, and institutions in a respective environment. (H2) The inclusion and participation of relevant and interested actors (individuals

and diverse forms of their association and organisation), including diverse social minorities, in the formulation and adoption, as well as in the implementation of (crisis) processes, policies, and measures improve their legitimacy.

Two specific hypotheses are: (H3) Crisis management processes, policies, and measures in diverse environments impact and hurt minorities more than the rest of the population. (H4) Formal and informal inclusion and participation of diverse minorities, persons belonging to them, and particularly their representatives in the formulation, adoption, and implementation of crisis management processes, strategies, policies, and measures can improve their legitimacy, acceptance, and effectivity within those communities and respective societies.

The following section briefly presents the literature review as the basis and framework for the section on conceptual and methodological discussion as well as for the conclusion. Through presenting some preliminary results of the LEGITIMULT project, the results of other projects, and the research programme of the Institute for Ethnic Studies (IES), these sections address some key concepts, as well as terminological, conceptual, and methodological questions relevant to the study of the legitimacy of crisis management processes, strategies, policies and measures in general, and particularly from the perspective of diverse minorities, as well as (the implementation of) the principle of non-discrimination.

2. Literature Review^{iv}

As mentioned, SARS-CoV-2 virus and COVID-19 pandemic related content has dominated local, national, and global media, as well as the academic press over the past few years, more precisely since the end of 2019. The volume of broadcasted radio and TV programs, published news, commentaries and reports (see, e.g., 24ur.com, BBC, CNBC, DW, MMC), popular and scholarly articles, papers and studies published in scientific journals (e.g., *Nature* with more than 18 thousand search results, *Science* with more than 650 search results, *The Lancet* with more than 9,690 search results by March 2023, etc.), and scholarly books in all sciences and almost all fields is enormous. It is almost impossible to imagine the number and volume of real and fake, individual and collective, relevant and irrelevant contributions, news, blogs, shared contents, b/vlogs, and comments on the web.^v

Consequently, working on a comprehensive literature review of SARS-CoV-2 virus, pandemic and COVID-19 crisis management-related content is a complex task, even when focused on specific topics and contexts. Searching in general search engines (e.g., Google, Yahoo), selected national and international media databases, and various digital databases^{vi} for the relevant literature and sources published between the end of 2019 and February 2023 (in addition to those in English, also those in Croatian, German, Italian and Slovene), we used search terms related to human and minority rights, the protection of minorities, minority and border communities, and the principle of non-discrimination. While studying the legitimacy of COVID-19 pandemic related crisis management in diverse environments and at various levels of government in European countries, the LEGITIMULT project's literature review focuses on:

- legitimacy (e.g., Beetham 2012; Buchanan 2002; Caby & Frehen 2021; De Fine Licht et al. 2014; Esaiasson et al. 2012; Jackson et al. 2012),
- the approaches to and concepts, strategies, policies, and measures of crisis management in general and specifically during the COVID-19 pandemic (e.g., Ansel et al. 2010; Christensen et al. 2016; Christensen & Ma 2021; Rodríguez et al. 2018),

- the roles of all branches of government, and particularly of legislation in crisis management processes (e.g., Bolleyer & Salát 2021; Chaplin 2020; Petrov 2020),
- democracy, the inclusion, integration and participation of citizens, citizens' perspectives on pandemic-related crisis management, and particularly on crisis management policies, measures, and their impacts and consequences (e.g., Alsan et al. 2020/2023, Bohle et al. 2022; Cronert 2022; Edgell et al. 2021; Engler et al. 2021; Gidengil et al. 2022; Guasti & Bustikova 2022; Heinzl & Liese 2021; Lowande & Rogowski 2021; Lozano et al. 2021; Maerz et al. 2020; Mouter et al. 2021; Rump & Zwiener-Collins 2021; Stasavage 2020).

Considering their social relevance, logically, the issues of legitimacy, human rights, equality and minorities appeared in media reports and content rather early in the COVID-19 pandemic, particularly in the context of the introduction of limitations, lockdowns and various restrictive measures, but also regarding access to adequate health and other public services for people in different environments (e.g., BBC, DW). More precisely, the following issues were addressed: the interference with human rights, constraints, restriction(s), limitation(s) and temporary suspension/derogation of human rights, the extent and reciprocity of introduced measures, as well as the fact that diverse, particularly marginalized groups and minorities, but also border communities, were over-proportionally affected by COVID-19 crisis policies, measures and restrictions. However, in most cases, media reports, discussions, concerns, and warnings, as well as various expressions of public concern and dissatisfaction did not seem to significantly influence the crisis management processes or the authorities, particularly the executive in formulating, adopting, and executing their strategies, policies and measures in the respective environments. Explaining and justifying their position and actions, the authorities claimed that the crisis demanded urgent and immediate decisions and actions, including radical ones, such as lockdowns and other restrictive and repressive measures. They concluded that, consequently, there was no time for time-consuming, uncertain, and possibly ineffective (extensive) public consultations, inclusive democratic processes and decision making. When faced with a life or death situation, in their view, sacrificing some human rights and democracy by neglecting and limiting democratic inclusion and participation in decision-making was necessary and the price worth paying. After all, the experiences of “the war on terror(ism)” showed that people can accept certain limitations to human rights and might be willing to trade some rights for the promise, even a false one, of safety and security (Žagar 2020; 2023).

The COVID-19 pandemic and related crises immediately attracted the attention of researchers in social sciences and humanities. The first studies, research reports, and scholarly publications appeared in 2020. Their number and volume increased substantially in subsequent years. Among the LEGITIMULT partners, for example, the Institute for Ethnic Studies immediately began to study the impact and consequences of COVID-19 related crisis management strategies on ethnic minorities, particularly in Slovenia and neighbouring countries. The first results (11 scholarly papers based upon various research approaches and methods) were published in the thematic issue (No. 85) of the *Treatises and Documents, Journal of Ethnic Studies* in December 2020, and an extensive scholarly monograph in Slovene followed in 2021 (Munda Hirnök & Novak Lukanović 2021). Research at Eurac Research contributed to the edited volume on comparative federalism and COVID-19 (Steytler 2021)^{vii} and the study on the impact and consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on linguistic minorities and border communities in the South Tyrolean Political Science Association (Pallaver et al. 2021).

Our review of scholarly publications and literature (in social sciences and humanities, but also in other sciences and fields) in the beginning of 2023 shows that these frequently mention issues relevant to our topic. Among these, we could list human rights, their limitation, suspension and/or derogation, cases of possible discrimination, and the inclusion and participation of citizens (and the population in general) in decision making or – more precisely – the lack thereof (resulting in exclusion) that leads to the strengthening of the executive and could result in a democratic deficit and in the rise of illiberal policies. However, only a small share of publications and literature focus on these issues and address them in-depth or holistically. Focusing on human rights, cases of direct and indirect discrimination, border communities, the rights, position and protection of diverse minorities, their inclusion, integration, and participation in crisis management process, the impact(s) and consequences of (particularly restrictive and/or repressive) crisis management measures on those communities, as well as on their perceptions regarding those issues, the number of the relevant titles is smaller but still substantial.^{viii}

Our literature review shows that human rights, including the rights of minorities, are among the first victims of crises and crisis management. The Croatian Ombudswoman's report on the situation of human rights and equality in the country in 2021 (Pučka pravobraniteljica 2022a), and her recommendations for better resilience to future crises based on her assessments of the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on human rights and equality (Pučka pravobraniteljica 2022b), confirm such a conclusion. These practices of authorities, particularly disproportional limitations or the suspension of human rights, restrictive and repressive measures, as well as other possible human rights violations that can provoke resistance in the people cannot be considered legitimate democratic crisis management (Huffstetler et al. 2021; Žagar 2021).

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed existing (often long-term) inequalities, including social, economic, ethnic, and racial inequality, in contemporary societies and created new ones (Katikireddi et al. 2021; Platt & Warwick 2020). As consequences of those inequalities, often economically and socially de-privileged individuals, members of diverse minorities, including ethnic and racial ones, migrants, refugees, and marginalized individuals and groups frequently experience(d) additional vulnerability and exposure to the virus, the worsening of pre-existing health conditions and illnesses (e.g., diabetes, obesity, hypertension, cardiovascular problems), and lesser access to (public) healthcare and other services. The data show that they often suffered excess mortality compared with the rest of the population (Kumar et al. 2021; OECD 2022).

The negative impacts of the pandemic and crisis require recovery and resilience plans and measures at all levels aimed at improving equal access to public services, reducing the digital divide, promoting gender equality and inclusion, and preventing all types of violence. They should consider women, children and young people, older people, people with disabilities, people in precarious working conditions, homeless people, diverse social minorities, including national, ethnic, language and religious minorities, the LGBTQIA+ community, and other diverse marginalized groups and individuals (FRA 2022; UN 2020).

Although the Roma are the largest ethnic minority in the European context, they could be considered the most marginalized minority that frequently experiences direct and indirect discrimination. The COVID-19 pandemic and related crisis management have widened long-standing exclusion, poverty and discrimination against the Roma, who often do not have access

to potable tap water, adequate housing and the sanitary facilities needed to follow preventive public health measures, while their access to healthcare could be limited. There were reports on disproportionate or militarized COVID-19 crisis measures targeting Roma neighbourhoods or towns, racist and discriminatory approaches to public health, racist narrative and discourse, as well as media reporting that cast the Roma as a collective health and safety threat in Bulgaria, Slovakia, Romania, and in other countries. In addition to the already poor inclusion and performance of Roma pupils in education in Slovenia and Europe, the suspension of regular school activities, remote learning during lockdown, and problems in establishing contact and collaboration between the teachers, Roma pupils and their parents because of technical conditions and lack of digital access are likely to have broader negative consequences for these pupils (Bešter & Pirc 2020; 2021; FRA 2020; Girard 2021; Matache & Bhabha 2020).

Systemic discrimination, socio-economic injustice, aggressive nationalism, exclusion, racism, and xenophobia frequently directed against minorities, migrants, foreigners, refugees, marginalized groups and individuals, defined as “the others”, existed long before the COVID-19 pandemic. These escalated with the growing populism and ideology of illiberal democracy. During the COVID-19 crisis, they escalated further and disproportionately affected these target populations. In the initial stages of the pandemic, when people were guessing about the possible origins of the virus, a growth in anti-Asian racism was detected. Inclusion, integration, multi- and intercultural policies, democratic participation, and ongoing inclusive open public dialogue could be useful approaches to deescalating and preventing social exclusion, populism, exclusivism, discrimination, aggressive nationalism, racism, and xenophobia (Elias et al. 2021; Žagar 2023).

The goal of the toolkit of the Council of Europe, which is based upon anti-discrimination, diversity, inclusion, and democratic participation, is to ensure that crisis management measures are proportionate to the evaluated risk and have clear time limits. Particularly important for border regions and minorities are information, communication, inclusion, and multi-level cooperation with all relevant actors, including civil society and specific communities (Cramer Marsal et al. 2020, 11–25; Engler et al. 2021; Jurić Pahor 2020).

As the case of the Slovene national minority in Austria shows, social interaction within the minority and broader, flexible (internal and external) communication, organisational capacity, and ability to adapt to the changed situation and COVID-19 crisis management measures, as well as cooperation with its kin-state, proved crucial for the vitality and development of minorities. Consequently, they were able to respond to restrictive crisis measures, the cancellation of traditional events, and the closure of bilingual schools by organizing online and hybrid activities. However, restrictive measures are likely to have a long-lasting impact on a minority’s ethnic vitality. These developments confirmed the importance of the use of minority and regional languages in such situations and in crisis management in general in diverse societies. The online survey, conducted between March and June 2020, which aimed to analyse the extent to which communication in one’s mother tongue was assured by different stakeholders in the Member States of the EU, as well as among the members of the Federal Union of European Nationalities (FUEN), showed the importance of minority and regional languages in general, particularly during crisis situations. The availability of relevant information in one’s mother tongue, the public use of one’s mother tongue, mother tongue education, and other public services contribute to better social inclusion of minorities, as well

as to more successful, inclusive, legitimate, and democratic crisis management (FUEN 2020; Grafenauer & Jesih 2020; 2021).

South Tyrol is an interesting case study that shows how this autonomous province experienced the COVID-19 pandemic that impacted its life and politics, as well as how it reacted to the crisis within the framework of Italy's pandemic management (Pallaver et al. 2021). It opted for a special path legitimized through a law that the provincial parliament adopted with a large majority in May 2020. Although it was flexible in adapting to new local circumstances, resulting in more or less strict measures compared to the national emergency decrees, the special path has ultimately not turned out to be successful from an epidemiological point of view. Nor was the province's governance style radically different from the national one. The pre-existing socio-political cleavages continued and resulted in criticism of the special path. However, this path, shared by other Italian regions, presented a reaction against the centralized pandemic management of the Conte II government (Alber & Zgaga 2021).

3. Studying Legitimate Crisis Management – Methodological and Conceptual Discussion

Considering that there is no perfect approach and method in studying complex phenomena and concepts, the literature review confirms the relevance of the research questions and shows that authors recognize the importance of democratic and legitimate crisis management and governance. From their specific perspectives, they indicate different and diverse (f)actors, conditions, circumstances, approaches, strategic policies, measures, and actions that can contribute to more democratic and legitimate crisis management. There seems to be a general agreement that exclusive, restrictive, and repressive crisis management usually dominated by the executive had a negative impact on democracy. In many environments (not only in countries considered illiberal democracies), such crisis management might have contributed to the strengthening of populism and the ideology and practice of illiberal democracy.

Simultaneously, our literature review, previous research, and the first interviews within the project carried out in the summer and fall of 2023 confirm the relevance of the LEGITIMULT research design, approaches, and methods in studying the legitimacy of the COVID-19 related crisis management. Studying complex, dynamic, and constantly evolving (social) phenomena and concepts requires and stimulates constant, intense, open, and inclusive conceptual and methodological discussions. Focusing on crisis management, its legitimacy, as well as its consequences and impacts in respective environments upon individuals and distinct communities, particularly minorities, using, coordinating, combining, interpreting, constantly evaluating, and developing diverse (disciplinary, multi-, inter- and transdisciplinary) research approaches and methods as well as terminologies, concepts, definitions, theoretical models and theories seems to be the best research practice in this context. Additionally, intense and inclusive cooperation with relevant stockholders in diverse environments is needed, particularly in discussing the concept of legitimate democratic crisis governance, best practices and recommendations, as well as in developing and applying the toolbox highlighting the core elements of legitimate crisis governance. The approaches and practices of methodological pluralism (see e.g., della Porta & Keating 2008) used in studying socially relevant diversities, equality, inclusion, integration and participation of diverse minorities, distinct communities and persons belonging to them also prove useful in researching the democracy and legitimacy of crisis management and governance.

Considering specific research themes and tasks, various specific research approaches and methods are used and combined within the LEGITIMULT project. Applying quantitative approaches and methods, including statistical analysis adjusted to specific themes, the quantitative research applied by other Work Packages collects and analyses relevant data, while creating, developing and interpreting the databases on legitimate democratic crisis management in the MLG IGR context. As necessary inputs, these (quantitative) research results and findings are important for designing and executing successful qualitative research into the impacts and consequences of crisis management measures on human and minority rights, the protection and situation of diverse minorities and communities, as well as the principle of non-discrimination. Our qualitative research focuses particularly on the perceptions of those impacts and consequences by persons belonging to diverse minorities and distinct communities. Although the results of the qualitative research should not be generalized as they are contextually relevant and apply to specific case studies, they are important for the verification, evaluation, and interpretation of the data, results, and findings of quantitative research of other Work Packages.

Our qualitative research studies the attitudes and perceptions of persons belonging to social minorities (including marginalized groups and border communities) regarding the legitimacy and democratic nature of crisis management and governance, and the impact(s) of crisis management policies and measures. It focuses on the impacts of restrictive and repressive measures on human rights, the rights and position of minorities, the principle and policies of non-discrimination, and the consequences of those policies and measures. In addition to direct and indirect observation, informal conversations, and formal events, such as meetings, panels, workshops and/or focus groups, it is based on open-ended in-depth interviews. The initial interviewees were selected from our existing contacts. These include persons (particularly activists and representatives) belonging to minorities and distinct and/or marginalized groups and communities, such as national, ethnic, religious and language minorities, (im)migrants (in addition to documented also undocumented ones, if possible), refugees, homeless people, LGBTQIA+ communities and associations, etc. in Austria, Croatia, Italy, Slovenia and possibly other countries (e.g., Spain^{ix}). Additional interviewees will be determined using the snowball method.

We developed the concept and core questions for the open-ended in-depth interviews based on our previous research and the literature review. Proceeding from our existing contacts, cooperation and research,^x some informal conversations were held with a few members and representatives of various social minorities and institutions (e.g., national, ethnic and linguistic minorities, migrants, offices for migrant workers, gender and LGBTQIA+ activists in Slovenia, Austria, Croatia and Italy),^{xi} as well as selected researchers to test the concept and core questions of the open-ended in-depth interviews.^{xii} These conversations detected some difficulties and possible problems, particularly terminological and conceptual ones, that need to be addressed. Considering the varied social, economic, and educational background, status, and position of individual interviewees, there is a need to explain and clarify the terminology and concepts in detail in order for the interviewees to understand them fully. Namely, individual respondents understood the terminology and complex concepts used (such as democracy, inclusion, integration, participation, legitimacy, human rights, including rights and protection of diverse social minorities, the principle of non-discrimination, direct and indirect discrimination) in different ways. However, all respondents confirmed the importance of the informal and formal inclusion and the democratic participation of minorities and their

representatives in decision-making processes for the legitimacy of crisis management and the adopted decisions and measures in a certain environment.

Given this experience, all interviewees shall be offered the option to anonymize their interviews. Often, the persons belonging to minorities express that they want to have their names, work, positions within their minority community, and their views visible in the research documents, as well as in the findings and results in media and publications. This practice of taking into account the expressed wishes and interests of the interviewees is consistent with research ethics and rules.

The complexities and dynamics of social phenomena often result in multiple, possibly conflicting definitions and concepts that do not fully capture the ongoing, complex, interconnected, and evolving nature of these phenomena with their specific spatial, temporal, and relational dimensions. The LEGITIMULT project recognizes that researchers, in addition to specific research approaches and methods, also use their specific terminologies and definitions. These need to be presented, explained and coordinated. The participants in the informal conversations explained their understanding of key terms, concepts and definitions and assessed their importance from their specific perspectives, while considering the position, status, perceptions, worries, needs and interests of the respective minority communities. When discussing the interviews process, the members and representatives of various minority communities suggested that before the interviewer asks the core questions, the respondents should be asked to present their understanding and interpretation of certain terms. Their understanding of the concepts of legitimacy, legitimate democratic multilevel crisis management and governance in general and related to the COVID-19 pandemic, diverse social minorities, human and minority rights, inclusion, integration and participation would be of particular importance. The recommendation was that before the interviewees start answering the core interview questions, they should be given an explanation of how the researchers understand these terms, as well as which are the main goals, expected results and impacts of the study. The interviewers need to pay particular attention to the explanations of the concepts and definitions of legitimacy and multilevel democratic crisis governance, since these are not as well known or clear even to those with a social science or humanities background.

We recognize several definitions and concepts of social and political legitimacy that can be found in scholarly literature, including the ones by Locke and Weber.^{xiii} For the purpose of our study we can define legitimacy in the context of crisis management and governance simply as the popular acceptance of and agreement with the approaches, decision-making and practices of authorities at all levels. This also applies to specific strategies, policies, decisions, measures and activities within crisis management and particularly their execution, impacts and consequences in the respective social environments. Considering the attitudes of the people in a certain social environment, one could conclude that the higher the acceptance and agreement, the more legitimate the crisis management.

Legitimate democratic (multilevel) crisis management and governance presumes democratic inclusion, integration and participation of the people in accordance with democratic principles, rules and procedures in the development and formulation of crisis strategies and policies, in decision-making on crisis policies and measures at all levels of authority, as well as, ideally, in their execution. Confirming observations within the research project on political participation of minorities, our informal conversations pointed out that social activists, members and

representatives of diverse social minorities consider the inclusion and participation of persons belonging to respective minorities, as well as those minorities as collective entities, key indicators of the legitimacy and democracy of crisis management and governance. In this context, they stressed the importance of the social and political participation of diverse minorities for legitimacy and democracy in diverse and plural contemporary societies. There was a general agreement that democracy is a cherished social practice, value, principle and goal worth striving and fighting for.

Since there is no single, universally accepted definition of minorities, it was stressed that as a rule they are unequal and unprivileged, usually in a less favourable situation and status in comparison with the rest of the population, even if in some specific cases (e.g., women) they might be a numerical majority. It is important to recognize that social minorities and social majorities are internally diverse and plural. They are not homogenous and uniform. Consequently, both majorities and minorities could be observed as coalitions of diverse coalitions.

Our informal conversations and initial interviews within the LEGITIMULT project confirmed the research findings of the Institute for Ethnic Studies (IES). In particular, the basic research project, titled Political Participation of National Minorities and Persons Belonging to Them: Comparative Study of Political Participation of Slovene Minorities in the Neighbouring Countries of the Republic of Slovenia, the results of which were that as a consequence of the inclusion of diverse (social, specifically national and ethnic) minorities in all spheres of life, their social and political participation should be considered one of the most important criteria of democracy and democratic governance in respective environments. In this context, the theoretical model of social and political participation and representation of (national) minorities (Žagar 2017, 16–18), developed as a tool and yardstick for the IES study, proves useful in studying legitimacy. This theoretical model that evolves constantly specifies general approaches to political participation of (diverse social, particularly national) minorities, as well as concepts and types of and mechanisms for the political participation of minorities.

Among the **general approaches** to social and political participation of (national and other) minorities and persons belonging to them, the theoretical model lists: (I) constitutionally and/or legally regulated **formal participation** in legislation and in executive and consultative bodies; (II) **informal participation** in political processes and decision-making, as well as lobbying; (III) inclusion, membership and activism in **political parties (both mainstream and minority), movements, organisations and associations**; (IV) **(Neo)Corporatist approaches, arrangements, bodies, processes and mechanisms** (such as various forms of consultations and consultative bodies); (V) **consociative arrangements**, particularly elite power-sharing; (VI) inclusion and participation through **basic principles** of constitutional and international law, including human rights, rule of law, democracy and democratic participation, equal rights and equality, justice, non-discrimination, limited majority rule, special rights and protection of minorities; (VII) inclusion and participation through **inclusion and integration policies**; and (VIII) inclusion and **participation through specific systems and mechanisms of minority protection** (at all levels), based on the special rights of minorities (Žagar 2017).

Among the **concepts, types and mechanisms** of social and political participation of minorities that can provide for and promote their better inclusion and participation, the theoretical model includes: (I) **elections and electoral systems** that can provide (A) for formally guaranteed,

direct representation of minorities in the legislative (1) through reserved minority seats, (2) special minority thresholds for minority political parties and/or candidates, (3) over-proportional representation of minorities and/or minimal quotas of minority representatives on the lists of mainstream parties, or (B) for informal political arrangements and declarations, suggesting the mainstream political parties include a certain proportion of minority candidates on their electoral lists; (II) **informal agreements in political processes** and principles declared by statutes, programmes and other documents of **political parties** that should ensure (1) the inclusion and participation of minority politicians and representatives in mainstream political parties, including quotas for diverse minorities, (2) inter-party cooperation and consensus building on minority (related) issues, (3) the participation of minority political parties in political processes, including elections; (III) **special procedures of decision making** regulated by law or political agreements, including minority veto and obligatory or consultative opinions of minority institutions, organisations and/or representatives or joint consultative bodies that can ensure the adequate participation of minorities and realization of their specific interests; (IV) inclusion of minority representatives and elites in policy formulation and decision-making through various **(Neo)Corporatist and consociative arrangements** and/or (formal and informal) bodies and institutions at all levels of government that bring in the process-specific views and interests of diverse minorities; (V) **affirmative action and other affirmative measures** (sometimes called positive discrimination) that promote the inclusion, integration and participation of minorities; (VI) at least the proportional, if possible over-proportional, **employment (quotas) of persons belonging to minorities** in the public and private sectors that shall ensure an adequate number and proportion of persons belonging to minorities among public/civil servants in state administration and public institutions; (VII) **monitoring the situation, position and status of minorities and persons belonging to them** for which adequate internal and external mechanisms shall be established; (VIII) and **autonomies**, particularly minority autonomy that can be realized through diverse arrangements of self-rule and management at various levels (from local to national), such as formal (constitutional, legal, political) and informal autonomies, and territorial (federalism, regionalism) and non-territorial autonomies (such as cultural, functional and personal autonomy) (Žagar 2017).

Our informal conversations covered issues of human rights, minority rights, position and protection, possible cases of discrimination, (the realization of) anti-discrimination policies, and the principle of non-discrimination, all of which everybody considered to be of great importance. These conversations and the interviews within the LEGITIMULT project confirmed that the core interview questions appropriately addressed the relevant issues. There was a general agreement that the adopted and implemented crisis policies and measures, particularly restrictive and repressive ones, did impact human and minority rights and, at least in some cases, resulted in inequality and discrimination. Usually, they impacted diverse minorities more than the rest of the population. For example, in addition to the unpleasant consequences of lockdowns, which were felt by everyone, owing to the closure of international borders, including the borders between the Schengen countries, regular contact, and the intense economic and particularly cultural cooperation with their kin countries involving the daily mobility of national minorities were interrupted and/or prevented. The contacts, cooperation and mobility of these minorities are essential for their vitality and preservation of their specific cultures, ways of life, and identities, considering that contacts, cooperation with and support of respective kin states represent their traditional cultural background. From the perspective of border regions, all populations within those regions and their specific ways of life, we could conclude that they were also over-proportionally affected by the closures of international

borders, which made cross-border cooperation and exchange, international (daily) mobility and migration almost impossible (Grafenauer & Jesih 2020; 2021).

Although everybody was affected by lockdowns that limited or even prevented internal mobility and cut personal, cultural, social and economic links, contacts and cooperation, diverse minorities, particularly migrants, marginalized groups and individuals, felt the impacts and consequences of the lockdowns even more. Consequently, their marginalization and (social) exclusion, as well as the risk of being discriminated against increased, while their (social) inclusion and integration became still more difficult. Our literature review and research so far confirm that those in socially less favourable situations, particularly marginalized individuals and groups, did not have equal access to health and social care or to various (administrative and public) services, including medical services and education.

The reviewed literature, our previous research, the informal conversations, and the LEGITIMULT interviews confirm that developing and using more inclusive and democratic crisis management, and the inclusion and participation of interested social actors, including diverse minorities, in decision making, would contribute to more democratic and legitimate crisis management. The inclusion and participation of diverse minorities in democratic decision-making are important indicators of democracy and legitimacy in diverse societies that also apply in crisis situations.

Additionally, our literature review, previous research, the informal conversations, and the LEGITIMULT interviews indicate the relevance of our research questions and working hypotheses. They confirm that in diverse environments, formal and informal inclusion and participation of (ideally, all) minority communities, persons belonging to those minorities, particularly their leaders, activists, and (s)electd representatives in crisis management processes, the formulation and adoption of strategies, policies and measures, as well as their implementation/execution could improve their legitimacy (within minority communities and societies as a whole) and the democratic nature of crisis management and governance. This is true even if their inclusion and participation are only symbolic. Based on our literature review, previous research and the attitudes expressed in the informal conversations, we could conclude that crisis management processes, policies and measures (particularly restrictive and repressive ones) usually impact and hurt various minorities more than the rest of the population.

4. Conclusion

Our literature review, previous and preliminary research, our methodological, terminological and conceptual discussions, as well as the informal conversations and the LEGITIMULT interviews presented in the previous sections confirm the relevance of the LEGITIMULT project, its design and planned research. They provide an adequate basis and framework for future research into the perceptions and attitudes of persons belonging to various social minorities with regard to democracy and the legitimacy of crisis management at different levels of authority. The predominantly qualitative field research on the perceptions and attitudes of (selected) persons belonging to various social minorities regarding the legitimacy of COVID-19 related crisis management will focus on the inclusion and participation of minorities in the formulation of crisis management strategies, policies and measures, as well as their implementation, on the impacts and consequences of those strategies, policies and measures

regarding human rights, position, status, rights and protection of minorities, and the principle of non-discrimination.

We expect that the qualitative field research into selected minorities as specific case studies, and particularly open-ended in-depth interviews, will provide an insight into the perceptions and attitudes of persons belonging to these minorities with regard to the legitimacy and democracy of COVID-19 related crisis management and measures in respective environments. Additionally, the findings will be instrumental in evaluating and interpreting the results of the LEGITIMULT project, particularly those produced by quantitative approaches and methods within other Work Packages. This approach will contribute to the formulation of relevant recommendations and the development of a toolkit to ensure a better inclusion and democratic participation of relevant actors in decision-making in crisis management processes. This toolkit could be used by all stakeholders in respective environments at all levels and could help to improve the democracy and legitimacy of crisis management and governance in future crisis situations.

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Notes:

ⁱ See the LEGITIMULT project on legitimate crisis governance in multilevel systems: <http://legitimult.eu/> as well as: <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100089222897068>,

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/legitimultproject> and <https://twitter.com/legitimult>.

ⁱⁱ For a brief presentation of the LEGITIMULT Project's Work Package (WP4) on legitimate crisis governance in the context of human rights, minority rights, and the principle of non-discrimination, coordinated by the Institute for Ethnic Studies, see: <http://www.inv.si/DocDir/projekti/A%20brief%20presentation%20of%20the%20LEGITIMULT%20PROJECT.doc>.

ⁱⁱⁱ When used in this article, the term minority refers to a minority community as a collective (collective entity) as well as to individuals, i.e., persons belonging to this minority community. Although the minority rights, including the rights of national minorities, are mostly viewed as individual rights of persons belonging to those minorities, their collective dimension should also be considered.

^{iv} The team that developed the specific WP4 bibliography and literature review on the legitimacy of crisis management with regard to human rights, rights and protection of minorities and persons belonging to minorities, and the principle of non-discrimination of the LEGITIMULT project (available on the project's webpage) consists of Dr. Romana Bešter, Dr. Danijel Grafenauer, Dr. Boris Jesih, Dr. Janez Pirc, Dr. Sofija Zver and Prof. Dr. Mitja Žagar from the Institute for Ethnic Studies that coordinates the WP4, Prof. Dr. Ružica Jakešević, Prof. Dr. Đana Luša, Prof. Dr. Siniša Tatalović and Prof. Dr. Marta Zorko from the Faculty of Political Science, University of Zagreb, and Dr. Elisabeth Alber and Martina Gianola from the EURAC Research.

^v For example, the COVID-DEM Global Democracy & Pandemic Tracker (DEM-DEC, N/D) that ran from April 2020 to April 2022 contains over 3,000 items.

^{vi} E.g., national, regional and global ones, such as, *COBISS*, *Scopus*, *Web of Science*, on-line library catalogues, such as *Wiley Online Library*, as well as specialized data bases, such as *International Political Science Abstracts (IPSA)*, and on-line data bases of scholarly journals – in addition to those mentioned above, e.g., *East European Politics*, *Public Organization Review*, *Treatises and Documents*, *West European Politics*, etc.

^{vii} The publishing of this volume in open access was enabled by a partner consortium in which Eurac Research participated as a member of the International Association of Centers for Federal Studies (IACFS).

^{viii} A selected bibliography of those publications is available at the webpage of LEGITIMULT project (as an appendix to the Deliverable 1 of WP 4): <http://legitimult.eu/>.

^{ix} In Spain, through existing channels, there might be an opportunity to interview some undocumented migrants, thereby gaining access to their perceptions.

^x E.g., interviews on political participation of minorities carried out within the project titled Political participation of national minorities and persons belonging to them: Comparative study of political participation of Slovene

minorities in the neighboring countries of the Republic of Slovenia, which – although not planned initially – also addressed the consequences and impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic and pandemic-related crisis management.

^{xi} Some of them might be included in further research as interviewees.

^{xii} These informal conversations took place in various forms at different locations, mostly as person-to-person conversations at an agreed-upon or chance encounter/meeting and occasionally in the form of informal group discussion with a few participants. We chose these informal conversations in informal settings to test the core interview questions based on our previous experience with interviewees perceiving the interviews as formal settings to which they react accordingly. Namely, in formal settings people tend to adjust their behaviour, attitude, reactions, language and answers to their specific perception of the formal event.

^{xiii} Often presented in basic social science textbooks in secondary and higher education and all encyclopaedias.

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